

Collaborative standardization of key performance indicator assessment within NFDI using NocoDB

CoRDI 2025

RDM Infrastructures -
Assessment & People in RDM Infrastructure

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German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

A bottom-up, collaborative effort

Vision of the NFDI

“Data as a common good for excellent research, [...]”

Humanities and
Social Sciences

Engineering
Sciences

Natural Sciences

Life Sciences

- Scientific Domains develop data management **standards, tools**, and the necessary **research data infrastructure** in a community-guided process
 - Work in individual consortia is combined to create OneNFDI across all consortia
- **How to measure the success and impact on the scientific community at large?**

Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

Measures of success / progress / community adoption

- **Which KPIs are suitable and demanded measures?**
 - KPIs can be identified as:
 - internally defined by consortia in their proposals
 - measures supporting the NFDI Head Office: strategy / evaluation / reporting
 - indicators relevant for individual institutions as members of the NFDI
 - indicators relevant to political stakeholders evaluating the NFDI process
 - indicators demanded by the funder (DFG) to survey the progress of consortia
 - **DFG datasheet:** a table with a defined format now mandatory for progress reports
- **Heterogenous, yet conceptually similar or discretely overlapping indicators to collect**

Solving a demanding task with limited personnel?

“How to KPI” for consortia offices and the NFDI office

Landscape of tools to collect KPIs and curate them in practice

Scorpion

Other, custom solutions

Google Sheets

...

+ custom solutions
for tool interoperability

→ 2023: NFDI Management Circle Meeting in Freiburg

- *Reduce heterogeneity* of used tools in the consortia
- *Leverage synergy* through shared expertise
- Evaluate & *select most suitable tools* + GDPR compliance
- *Reduce setup and maintenance workload* for individual consortia

Significance of KPIs for the NFDI

NFDI collaborates on critical aspects

Harmonize:

- common understanding of reporting criteria (White Paper: Interim Report Reference)
- common understanding of the defined KPIs (DFG datasheet)
- Share best practice procedures and tool expertise across consortia offices
- Develop a set of KPIs assessing the overall NFDI process and success

→ **NocoDB as a common tool**

Why NocoDB?

User-friendly tables powered by a database structure

Build Databases As Spreadsheets : No-Coding Required

NocoDB allows building no-code database solutions with ease of spreadsheets.

Bring your own database or choose ours! Millions of rows? Not a problem.

Your Data. Your rules. You are in control.

The screenshot shows the NocoDB interface for a CRM system. The table has the following columns: #, Contact Name, Cotac..., Title, Profile Picture, Email, Subscription, Registration Nu..., and Paid Member. The data rows are as follows:

#	Contact Name	Cotac...	Title	Profile Picture	Email	Subscription	Registration Nu...	Paid Member
1.	Zain Lubin	321	Manager		zlubin@gmail.com	Pro	+8207461130782	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	Kierra Westervelt	322	Director		kierraw@gmail.com	Plus	+7047091633321	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	Wilson Curtis	323	Assistant		wilcurtis@outlook.com	Prime	+7893981497100	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4.	Emerson Dokidis	324	VP of Sales		emerson12@gmail.com	Pro	+3080455855339	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	Alfredo Westervelt	325	Engineer		alfredo.pasta@gmail.com	Pro	+2061017757126	<input type="checkbox"/>
6.	Terry Bator	326	HR Manager		terryb@gmail.com	Plus	+2173332610583	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
7.	Maria Geidt	327	CEO		Maria@gmail.com	Pro	+3410278098225	<input type="checkbox"/>
8.	Tatiana Bergson	328	CFO		Tatiana@outlook.com	Prime	+5641767475164	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
9.	Anika Bergson	329	Product Manager		abergson34@outlook.c...	Plus	+5780276410651	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

General introduction to NocoDB

NocoDB architecture

Source: <https://nocodb.com>

Benefits of the NocoDB system

How can NFDI (all stakeholders) profit?

Tables

- Reporting
- Publications**
- Events
- Services
- Digital_Artifacts
- Projects
- Collaborations
- Activities
- REF_Members
- REF_Persons
- REF_Partners
- REF_Entities
- REF_Fabio
- REF_Keywords
- REF_Datasheet

- **Centrally hosted** by the NFDI office
- **Training** for all consortia through direct support & video tutorials
- **Shared access** with clear role management
- **Collaboratively developed**, user-friendly table structure
 - Curation-tables vs. reference-tables
- **Standard tables** can be flexibly amended for individual needs without compromising comparability
- **Automatic retrieval of most DFG datasheet KPIs** with transparent tracing back to individual KPI records
- **Interoperability** with tools that are established in consortia

Status of NocoDB in the NFDI

Where do we stand?

- NocoDB is up and running at <https://nocodb.nfdi.de/> (non-public)
- Consortia are being onboarded, sandbox for testing available to all registered users
- Additional features and uses are being evaluated
- **Community momentum:** The NocoDB process facilitates strong by-in & collaboration

Significance beyond the NFDI

How can others benefit from this project?

- Has the potential to reduce person hour costs significantly
- NFDI gains significant experience in KPI collection in large-scale infrastructure projects
 - may be adopted by others
- showcases the value of cross-domain collaboration
 - administrative, research-supporting tasks, ...

Thank you for your attention!

Q&A?!

We'll stay in the room for the coffee break

To reach out after the conference

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Abstract and slides

